

FORMULATION AND *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL ANTI-ARTHRITIC TRANSDERMAL PATCH

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ABSTRACT

Background: Arthritis is characterized by painful inflammation and stiffness experienced in the joints. Since there is currently no known preventive measure or cure for arthritis, treatment primarily revolves around symptom management, with a special attention to reducing pain. Transdermal drug delivery provides localized relief from pain and inflammation associated with arthritis. It is more feasible alternative approach to conventional oral medications for long-term arthritis management.

Materials and Methods: The intent of the project was to develop transdermal patch containing blend of the polyherbal mixture of *Dichrostachy cinerea*, *Plecosperrum spinosum*, *Piper betel*, *Allium sativum* and *Piper nigrum* herbs having anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, analgesic, and anti-oxidant properties. Herbal transdermal patch was formulated using various ratios of HPMC E15 and xanthum gum as polymers with polyvinyl alcohol as plasticizer and polyethylene glycol as permeation enhancer.

Result: The transdermal patch underwent *in-vitro* evaluation, that includes physical appearance, thickness, folding endurance, weight uniformity, moisture content, pH and phytochemical screening of the formulated patches. Among these nine formulated patches, formulation 8 showed desirable characteristics of the transdermal patch and phytoconstituents were intact in the prepared patches.

Conclusion: The results obtained from the study, proved that a polyherbal mixture can be successfully formulated into a transdermal patch using HPMC E15, xanthum gum, polyvinyl alcohol and polyethylene glycol.

Keywords: Transdermal patch, arthritic, *Dichrostachy cinerea*, *Plecosperrum spinosum*, HPMC E15, xanthum gum, polyvinyl alcohol and polyethylene glycol.

I. INTRODUCTION

Arthritis comprises a cluster of conditions characterized by joint pain, swelling, warmth and tenderness, along with morning stiffness ^[1]. There are more than 100 different types of arthritis traced, among them osteoarthritis which is non-inflammatory arthritis and inflammatory arthritis (rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis,.) are most common, the inflammation can be caused by autoimmune processes ^[2]. There are various physical and chemical properties, genetic factors, and environmental factors involved in rheumatoid arthritis ^[3]. The degradation of cartilage, followed by the eventual deterioration of bone occurs when there is increase levels of inflammatory cytokines in the synovial joints, such as interleukin-6, interleukin-1 and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and others after coming into contact with an antigenic pathogen. According to WHO statistics, 18 million people worldwide suffered from rheumatoid arthritis, of those about 70% are female and 55% are over the age of 55 ^[4].

The allopathic medical system for treatment of rheumatoid arthritis includes the standard treatment regimens of glucocorticoids, disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs these currently available drugs either have certain side effects or are highly expensive ^[5]. Many medicinal plants offer an alternative treatment option for rheumatoid arthritis and researchers are increasingly interested in these plant-derived medicinal agents that are safe and efficient for herbal treatment formulations ^{[6][7]}. Herbal treatment combines the therapeutic experiences of numerous past generations with the methods of indigenous medical systems. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 60% of the world's population relies on herbal medicine and approximately 80% of the population in developing countries depends almost entirely on it for their primary health care needs ^[8].

In India, there are more than 2500 plants species which are currently used as herbal medicaments in the preparation of recent pharmaceuticals ^[9]. Large number of herbal extracts and products such as polyherbal formulations are prepared to reduce side effects and increase the benefits ^[10]. Herbal plants like *Dichrostachy cinerea*, *Plecosperrum spinosum*, *Piper betel*, *Allium sativum*, and *Piper nigrum* exhibits analgesic, anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritis properties due to presence of tannins, phenols, flavonoids, steroids and saponins.

The analgesic effects of *Dichrostachy cinerea* are mediated primarily through peripheral mechanisms, involving the inhibition of prostaglandin activity. Similarly, its anti-inflammatory effects are achieved through the inhibition of cyclooxygenase^{[11][12][13]}. The leave extract of *Dichrostachy cinerea* is utilized for massaging fractures and has anti-inflammatory potential^{[14][15]}.

The plants with antioxidant properties demonstrated the ability to reduce inflammation^[16]. Polyphenols are known to be key antioxidants, which neutralize the free radicals and therefore, are used in antioxidant formulations^[17]. The leaf extract of *Plecosperrum spinosum* contains elevated levels of secondary metabolites like phenols and flavonoids, these compounds make it a promising inhibitor of lipid peroxidation and protein oxidation. Consequently, *Plecosperrum spinosum* exhibits notable antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties^[18].

Betel, also known as *Piper betel*, is a member of the Piperaceae family and genus Piper, the plant known locally as sirih, is native to the middle and eastern peninsula of Malaysia^[19]. The flavonoids, alkaloids and other bioactive components of piper betel leaves are responsible for their anti-arthritic properties^[20].

Allium sativum, as cited in the Charaka Samhita, is recommended for treating arthritis and heart-related conditions. Local and tribal communities have historically utilized *Allium sativum* as a natural remedy for joint ailments^[21]. Extensive research supports the anti-inflammatory properties of allicin and sulfur compounds that are anti-inflammatory compounds and proved their role in treatment of arthritis^[22].

Piperine stands as the primary plant alkaloid derived from *Piper nigrum* which has analgesic, anti-convulsant, anti-tumor and anti-inflammatory activities^[23]. Its is traditionally used in Indian medicine to enhance the immune system^[24].

Transdermal delivery has emerged as one of the most advantageous methods among innovative drug delivery systems. Through effective design wide range of drugs can now be delivered using this advanced technology. Transdermal drug delivery offers several advantages, including maintaining an effective rate of drug administration over prolonged duration of time^[25]. Therapeutic substances through the skin offers a route that allows drugs to bypass initial degradation in the GIT or liver, that is first-pass metabolism when taken orally. Transdermal drug delivery presents a solution to the issue of poor patient compliance commonly observed with other methods of drug administration and this approach allows self-administration for patient^[26].

Xanthum gum which is a natural polymer was used for the formulation of polymer matrix of the transdermal patch. The primary structure of this naturally occurring xanthum gum consists of cellulosic backbone and trisaccharide side chain^[27]. FDA had approved xanthum gum for use of thickener and stabilizer. It is observed that the drug diffusion from the film is controlled by increasing the amount of xanthum gum which results in high swell ability of the film^[28].

Understanding the important role of natural herbs and advantages of transdermal patch for local effect in management of arthritis, in the present study we plan to design and formulate polyherbal mixture with anti-arthritic activity into a transdermal patch.

II. METHODS

A. Aqueous extraction of *Dichrostachy cinerea* and *Plecosperrum spinosum*:

Dichrostachy cinerea and *Plecosperrum spinosum* was extracted with distilled water by hot percolation method^[29]. The dried leaves of *Dichrostachy cinerea* and *Plecosperrum spinosum* were crushed and percolated with distilled water for about 2 hours and filtered. The extracts were concentrated by drying on water bath.

B. Preparation of polyherbal mixture^[30]:

The aqueous extract of *Dichrostachy cinerea*, *Plecosperrum spinosum* was blended with *Piper betel*, *Allium sativum* and *Piper nigrum*. The mixture obtained was filtered using Whatman filter paper and further evaporated and obtained concentrated mixture which was used to formulate transdermal patch.

C. Phytochemical screening of polyherbal mixture:

The standard procedures were followed to confirm the presence and absence of carbohydrates, protein, alkaloids, tannins, phenols, flavonoids, steroids, saponins^{[31][32]}.

D. Preparation of polyherbal transdermal patch by solvent casting method^{[33][34]}:

Solvent-casting procedure was the procedure adapted for preparation of transdermal patches. Initially 10 ml of distilled water was gently heated, to this desired quantity of polyvinyl alcohol and xanthum gum were added and stirred and cooled for half an hour. Later, HPMC E15 and polyethylene glycol was added to the above solution with constant stirring. The measured amount of polyherbal mixture was added into the polymer solution and stirred using magnetic stirrer set at 400 rpm for 20 min to obtain a uniform solution and sonicated for 20 min. This uniform solution was then poured into petri plate and kept in oven at 25°C – 50°C for about 5-12 hours to get desired transdermal patch^[35].

Total nine transdermal patches were formulated with two variable factors that is xanthum gum and HPMC E15 of three levels. Complete components description of each transdermal film is shown in Table 1.

E. *Formulation of polyherbal transdermal patch:*

I. TABLE

Formulation code	Xanthum gum in mg	HPMC in mg	Polyvinyl Alcohol in mg	Polyethylene glycol in ml	Solvent in ml
F1	10	100	30	1	10
F2	20	100	30	1	10
F3	30	100	30	1	10
F4	10	150	30	1	10
F5	20	150	30	1	10
F6	30	150	30	1	10
F7	10	200	30	1	10
F8	20	200	30	1	10
F9	30	200	30	1	10

COMPOSITION OF POLYHERBAL TRANSDERMAL PATCH:

F. *Physiochemical evaluation of polyherbal transdermal patch:*1) *Physical appearance:*

The prepared patches underwent a visual inspection, assessing attributes such as color, clarity, flexibility, and smoothness.

2) *Weight uniformity:*

The prepared patches were sectioned into various parts and each section was weighed using a digital balance. The average weight was then calculated from the individual weights.

3) *Thickness:*

The thickness of the formulated film was measured at 3 different points using a digital vernier caliper and average thickness of these three reading was calculated.

4) *Surface PH:*

The prepared patch surface pH was determined by cutting 1*1cm² part at three different position of the patch and the average pH was calculated. The patches are kept in 0.5 ml distilled water and thus allowed to swell for 1hour. The surface pH is determined by digital pH meter ^[36].

5) *Percentage of moisture content:*

Patches were weighed correctly and then kept inside a desiccator contained with calcium chloride (anhydrous). After completion of 3 days, the patches kept within the desiccator were removed and then weighed using an electronic balance. The moisture content (%) of transdermal patches was computed by the formula ^[37].

$$\% \text{Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

6) *Folding endurance:*

The efficacy of the plasticizer was investigated with the folding endurance test. The folding endurances of prepared patches were measured manually by the procedure of repetitively folding at the same position until the test patch breaks. The number of folding times for tested transdermal patches folded up the same position without breakage of the patches was taken as the measure of folding endurance ^[38].

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening on the polyherbal mixture was performed to confirm the presence of phytoconstituents with anti-arthritic activity.

II. TABLE

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF POLYHERBAL MIXTURE.

Sl.no	Test	Result
1	Test for Carbohydrates	+
2	Test for Proteins	-
3	Test for Alkaloids	-
4	Test for Tannins	+
5	Test for Phenols	+
6	Test for Flavonoids	+
7	Test for Saponins	+
8	Test for Steroids	+

'+' indicate present and '-' indicate absent

The results of phytochemical screening conducted on the polyherbal mixture is depicted in the Table number 2 which confirms the presence of carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, steroids while indicating the absence of proteins, alkaloids.

Formulation of polyherbal transdermal patch.

The current study aimed to develop a transdermal patch using the solvent casting method to create matrix-type patch. Xanthum gum and HPMC E15 was employed as the polymer for development of these patches, in addition polyvinyl alcohol was used as plasticizer and polyethylene glycol as permeation enhancer were utilized for formulation of polyherbal transdermal patch.

Nine formulations of transdermal patches containing polyherbal mixture with different ratios of xanthum gum and HPMC E15 were developed. Among these formulations F1, F2, and F4 did not meet the promising criteria, as the formulated transdermal patches were unable to be removed from the petri dish. This could be due to the low content of the polymer.

Whereas formulation F3, F5, F6, F7, F8 and F9 were able to be removed easily from the petri dish. These patches were flexible, smooth, and dark green in color. These patches were evaluated for physiochemical properties that are thickness, folding endurance, weight variation, and moisture content and results are shown in table number 3.

FIG 1: POLYHERBAL TRANSDERMAL PATCH

III. Table

PHYSIOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL TRANSDERMAL PATCH:

Formulation code	Thickness [mm]	Folding endurance	Weight uniformity [mg]	Percentage of moisture content [%]	Surface pH
F3	0.31±0.02	> 300	32.66±2.05	17.27±2.02	8.1
F5	0.38±0.02	> 300	36.66±1.24	11.82±1.25	7.8
F6	0.40±0.01	> 300	39.66±1.24	10.05±1.89	7.8
F7	0.41±0.01	> 300	40±1.63	12.25±2.34	8.3
F8	0.43±0.04	> 300	41±1.41	9.76±0.32	7.9
F9	0.45±0.01	> 300	41±0.81	9.78±2.12	8.1

To ensure uniformity in thickness, each patch was assessed at three different positions and the average was calculated. Thickness measurements revealed variations among the formulations depicted in the table 3, revealing variations ranging from 0.31mm to 0.45mm, with F9 being the thickest (0.45±0.01mm) and F3 is the thinnest (0.31±0.02 mm). The thickness increased with this increase in the polymer content.

The patch evaluated for weight variation shown good uniformity with low standard deviation, indicating uniform distribution of the polyherbal mixture in the matrix of the prepared patches. The weight variation of the prepared patches ranging from 32mg to 41mg. This indicates that the weight increases with increase in polymer content. Thickness and weight variation are important characteristic of the transdermal patch as it influences the rate of drug release and overall efficacy of the patch.

The formulated polyherbal transdermal patches exhibited folding endurance more than 300 which is due to the use of plasticizer in the formulation. It is essential for mechanical strength and durability of the patch. A higher folding endurance indicates better durability and resistance to stress^[39]. Low residual solvent content (17.27 - 9.76%), which helped the patches to remain stable. The greatest moisture content 17.27±2.02% was found to be in F3 and the least amount of moisture content 9.76±0.32% was found to be in F8 patch. Formulation 8 which has minimal moisture content could be advantageous with respect to stability and longer shelf life^[40].

The pH test for transdermal patches is necessary to ensure that the pH of the formulation is within the acceptable range for skin compatibility and minimize skin irritation^[41]. All the formulations pH falls into physiological skin pH which is safe to use on the skin.

The procedure ensured that the activity of the active pharmaceutical ingredients that is polyherbal mixture remains unaffected by performing phytochemical screening on the formulated polyherbal transdermal patch that confirms the presence of carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, steroids.

IV. CONCLUSION

By present study, it was successfully formulated polyherbal anti-arthritis transdermal patch and evaluated for all the desired properties. Further studies are need to be assessed for its anti-arthritic activity.

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